

Study of Saponins from *Trigonella foenum-graecum* Linn. Leaves

I. P. VARSHNEY and D. C. JAIN

Department of Chemistry, G. S. Institute of Technology and Science, Indore 452 003

and

H. C. SRIVASTAVA and P. P. SINGH

Chemistry Division, Ahmedabad Textile Industry's Research Association, Ahmedabad 380 015

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The leaves of *Trigonella foenum-graecum* Linn. yields three saponin glycosides named as Graecunin A, Graecunin B and Graecunin C. Graecunin B has been identified as a glycoside of diosgenin with glucose, xylose and rhamnose as sugars in the molar ratio of (4 : 1 : 2).

TRIGONELLA foenum-graecum Linn. is a member of the family Leguminosae, sub-family papilionaseae, commonly known as 'Maithi' in Hindi. The family Leguminosae is known to be a rich source for the saponins and sapogenins both triterpenic and steroidal¹. Leaves are used as vegetable throughout India.

A review of the literature shows that the seeds contain diosgenin^{2-6,8}, gitogenin^{2,3-5,6}, tigogenin^{2,4-6,8}, yuccagenin⁶, yamogenin⁸, neotigogenin² and the stem contains diosgenin and an unidentified genin⁷. In spite of all these works on sapogenin contents no work is reported on saponins and therefore this work was taken up. The present paper deals with the saponins from the leaves of this plant.

The green plants were purchased from the local market and the leaves and stems were separated and air dried. Powdered leaves were exhausted with petroleum ether and then with ethanol. The ethanol extract on concentration under reduced pressure gave a greenish brown syrupy mass, which was successively exhausted with petroleum ether, ether, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, ethyl acetate and acetone in order to remove the substances soluble in these solvents. This gave a dark brown syrupy mass which was then dissolved in minimum quantity of methanol and precipitated in a large volume of ether/acetone. It gave a light brown powder, which gave all the tests for the steroidal saponins. On TIC it showed the presence of three major and a number of minor products and therefore it was chromatographed on silica gel column using chloroform : methanol : water (65 : 35 : 10) as eluant (40 fractions).

Fractions giving identical single spot on TLC were combined and the fractions giving mixtures were further separated by rechromatography using chloroform : methanol : water (20 : 12 : 3) as eluant and finally each product was rechromatographed on alumina column using petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, acetone and methanol as eluants which gave 3 pure saponins named as Graecunin A, B and C, respectively. The purity of the saponins was confirmed by TLC and electrophoresis.

Graecunin B had m.p. 154-56°, $[(\alpha)]_D - 46.8$ (C-1%, MeOH) and R_f value (0.20) in chloroform : methanol : water (65 : 40 : 10). Graecunin B on acid hydrolysis with 2*N* sulphuric acid under reflux for 4 hours gave a genin which was separated and identified as diosgenin by m.p., m.m.p., I.R. and TLC with authentic sample of diosgenin.

The hydrolysate was neutralized with freshly precipitated barium carbonate and deionised by ion exchange resin (Amberlite IRA 400 and IR 120 (H⁺)). The sugar solution on concentration and chromatography on Whatman filter paper No. 1 showed the presence of three sugars identified as glucose, xylose and rhamnose. The sugars were reduced with sodium borohydride to alditols, which were acetylated in the usual manner and yielded alditol acetates.

The alditol acetates were injected in the GLC apparatus where 3% ECNSS on Chromosorb-W column was used and showed the presence of three sugars identified as glucose, xylose and rhamnose present in the molar ratio 4 : 1 : 2 (Fig 1). All the seven moles of the three sugars are therefore attached at C-3 OH group of diosgenin.

Fig. 1

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References

1. I. P. VARSHNEY, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 446.
2. R.E. MARKER, et al. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2242.
3. MME. S. HEITZ, *Comp. rend.*, 1959, 248, 283.
4. I. P. VARSHNEY and S. C. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 564.
5. F. R. Y. FAZLI and R. HARDMAN, *Tropical Science*, 1968, 10, 66.
6. S. GHOSAL, D. C. CHATTERJEE, S. K. GUPTA and S. K. BHATTACHARYYA, *Proc. 58th Ind. Sci. Cong. 1971*, Abstracts Part II, p. 197.
7. I. P. VARSHNEY and A. R. SOOD, *Ind. J. Appl. Chem.* 1971, 34, 219-220.
8. A.M. DAWLDER, A. A. SALCH, S. L. ELMOTEL, *Plant Med.* 1973, 24, 367-70.